

State of Public Sector Risk Management implementation in Germany

Abstract

While many studies assess risk management in a private sector context, public sector risk management and particularly with a focus on German municipalities is lagging behind. One main question in this regard is what factors drive the implementation of risk management in German municipalities. This article addresses that research gap by means of a structural equation model. The results evidence that the stage of risk management implementation is positively related to six factors and the implementation stage of risk management is positively related to the quality of risk management. The organisation size shows a moderating effect on the results.

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1 Introduction

In recent years the topic of risk management has emerged to a new level of importance in the public sector (Domokos et al., 2015). Risk management describes a process to identify and prevent risks with a systematic identification, analysis, evaluation, monitoring and active management of risks. It aims to ensure that public funds are used appropriately, intends to create transparency and provides an overview of the risk situation (Wengert, 2013). A systematically implemented risk management helps the fulfilment of management responsibilities. Increasing the effectiveness of risk management activities, this development has also become of interest for the public sector. Whereas municipalities in Anglo-Saxon countries are well advanced in the implementation of risk management (Offerhaus, 2009), for German municipalities it still is a new instrument.

The aftermath of scandals such as the delayed opening and large cost overruns when building the Berlin Brandenburg airport (Eisenring, 2014) or a city employee in Munich who got arrested for embezzlement (Thieme, 2014) show that the German public sector is not spared from such as misplanning, fraud and corruption. Financial mistakes, defaults on tax revenue, adverse developments in the financial markets and a variety of other risks in municipalities may jeopardize the achievement of strategic objectives (RiskNET, 2014). Consequently, public sector administration and its stakeholders demand greater oversight of key risks and initiatives to improve risk and internal control systems.

Initiatives in national and international regulations and frameworks specified for the public sector reflect the new urge for a higher awareness of the value of risk management. An example are Bavarian municipalities, which under Article 61 paragraph 3 of the Municipalities Code are obliged "to minimize financial risks" in the management of the household economy (Gemeindeordnung für den Freistaat Bayern, 1998). In addition, most states in the municipal budget ordinance declare that municipalities must report risks in their management report. However, apart from Bavaria, other German states do not express how risks need to be managed and overcome. While the management of risks slowly finds its way into the legislation, not all organisations have adopted it. Little is known about why some public administrations implement risk management while others do not. An understanding of the forces that drive risk management implementation enables a municipality and other stakeholders to know where

to obtain support and to strengthen the positive influences from the drivers. This will assist various stakeholders such as policy makers and founders of risk management initiatives who might be interested in knowing the impact of their initiatives. Against this background, the study aims to examine (i) which forces drive the implementation of risk management, (ii) if different forces drive the implementation of risk management in small and big municipalities and (iii) if a further developed risk management leads to a higher quality of risk management.

To further contribute to the public-sector literature, eight research questions regarding a selected set of risk management components are examined based on theoretical and empirical reasoning. To summarize, this paper examines if contingency characteristics affect the stage of risk management implementation in public administrations by using PLS-SEM.

Risk management is described as organizational activities and a continuous process for managing risks, which includes the functions of the enterprise-wide identification, assessment, management and monitoring of risks (International Organisation for Standardisation, 2009). Traditional, silo-based risk management primarily considers the management of individual, independent risks without its interactions. In today's approach, risk management becomes more holistic, also referred to as Enterprise Risk Management (ERM).

The modern version of risk management (ERM) is built on the skeleton of traditional risk management (Hampton, 2015), which will be the approach for this study applied to the circumstances of the public sector. Risk management in the public sector forms a part of a broader governance framework and identifies risk management and internal control as defining principles of good governance (Woods, 2009).

For the theoretical foundation to derive the research questions, different organizational theoretical approaches are applied to be able to explain key influences on the risk management adoption status in the public sector. The usage of the contingency approach is for recognising the influence of organisational context upon risk management (Chenhall, 2003). Literature proves that public and private sector risk management are different (Fone & Young, 2000; Woods, 2009). Contingency theory

suggests that organisational characteristics are influenced by organisations external, non-controllable as well as organisations internal, controllable contextual factors such as environment, technology and an organisations size (Chenhall, 2003).

Agency theory takes an important role saying that individuals always pursue their self-interest. Because of information asymmetries, agency costs occur to the principal in the form of surveillance and control costs to prevent of loss of welfare (Fama & Jensen, 1983). Control mechanisms can be seen as a central element of agency theory, having instruments such as risk management to reduce agency costs, which is why agency theory is of high relevance for this work (Burger & Schmelter, 2012).

Neo institutional theory is based on contingency theory and explains why and how institutions emerge in a certain way within a given context. Structures, processes and systems within organizations are a result of the incorporation of existing, institutionalized society concepts, and do not primarily base on economic cost-benefit calculus (Arwinge, 2013). Many practices, processes, locations and departments set up in organisations are due to the expectations of relevant stakeholders (Meyer & Rowan, 1977). For this work neo institutional theory is applied in the context of factors that primary creates benefit to a stakeholder in the form of legitimacy instead of cost-benefit calculus. For example it is expected that the implementation stage of risk management depends on trends and regulatory developments which grants the organisations legitimacy (Eisenhardt, 1988).

This paper both adapts factors from existing theory and develops or reformulates a new set of factors that are specifically suited to the context of German municipalities.

2 Literature review and research questions

Despite many studies focussing on risk management in various industries, very few studies focus on public administration and factors that influence the implementation stage of risk management, the most important of which is the study of Woods (2009). Many factors that are associated with the stage of risk management adoption do not necessarily apply to the organisational construct of the public-sector administration, which is why they should be considered separately. But to the best of our knowledge,

no literature examines factors that affect the stage of implementation of risk management in German public administrations.

Conversely, the question of which factors are linked to the extent of the risk management implementation has received diverse attention in the context of privately owned companies and many studies have been published. In this study evidence from research in the private sector is examined and reflected on transferability to the public sector. These studies are further explained in the remainder of this section followed by the development of the research question.

2.1 Executive support

An important aspect to consider when successfully implementing risk management is having executive support. Support from the top is essential and should begin with the Board of Directors (Marchetti, 2012). The responsibility for risk management rests with the board of directors (Woods, 2009). COSO (2004), Sobel and Reding (2004) and Kleffner et al. (2003) show the dependency of an effective risk management on active participation by the board of directors. Furthermore, Daud et al. (2011) and Yazid et al. (2011) show that the quality of board of directors affects the level of risk management adoption. Gordon et al. (2009) argue that the relation between firm performance and risk management is contingent upon board of director's monitoring. Moreover, Beasley et al. (2005) find that a higher percentage of independent members of the board of directors is positively related to the implementation stage of risk management. The above literature emphasizes the importance of the board of directors when implementing risk management. Whereas the executive committee of a private institution usually is named board of directors, the executive committee of a municipality mostly is represented by the council or city council. Assuming transferability, we adapt the term to the context of municipalities.

The relationship between the executive and a municipality's administration is that of a principal-agent. The council decides on strategic objectives of the administration and is responsible for the fulfilment of public tasks. The executive as well ensures an economical and quality-conscious management and effective controlling, where it can determine, for example, whether the implementation of a risk management is necessary to fulfil these tasks. Thus, we propose the following research question:

RQ1. Is there a positive relationship between explicit calls from the executive of the municipality and the municipalities' stage of risk management implementation?

2.2 Competence

Looking at the control environment of COSO's IC Framework, four out of the seven principals are directly or indirectly related to employee's competence (COSO, 1992; COSO, 2013). Competence in the context of this paper refers to any specialist skills or experience which may be related to risk management (COSO, 2013). A lack of critical thinking can lead to control failures because people do not understand the process (Pfister, 2009). Pfister (2009) identifies competence as a main driver for control effectiveness. Zhao et al. (2015) show that a lack of internal knowledge, skills and expertise relevant to risk management hindered the risk management implementation. Furthermore a lack of qualified personnel with knowledge, skills and expertise to implement risk management significantly hinders the risk management implementation (Zhao et al., 2015). The responsibility for establishing and maintaining adequate skills is the responsibility of management. However, they themselves must also have the necessary skills to carry out its role with regard to the design of the risk management (IFAC, 2013). Pfister (2009) identifies competence as a main driver for control effectiveness. Zhao et al. (2015) show that a lack of internal knowledge, skills and expertise relevant to risk management hindered the risk management implementation of Singapore-based Chinese construction firms. Furthermore a lack of qualified personnel with knowledge, skills and expertise to implement risk management significantly hinders the risk management implementation (Zhao et al., 2015). Agency theoretical considerations support the positive relationship between competence and risk management adoption status since the higher the competence of a principal, the better he is able to develop a risk management that hinders the agent to exploit information asymmetries.

Thus, we question if in German municipalities, competence in risk management leads to a further developed risk management:

RQ2. Does employee competence participating in risk management affect the municipalities' stage of risk management implementation positively?

2.3 Legal regulations

One possible explanation for a municipality to implement risk management is the change of regulations and requirements regarding effective corporate governance. Organisations in various industries have implemented risk management for compliance and corporate governance requirements (Kleffner et al., 2003). Literature confirms that the implementation of risk management has been compelled by legal requirements for compliance and corporate governance. Kleffner et al. (2003) identify in their studies examining companies in Canada that compliance with Toronto Stock Exchange guidelines is the reason for adopting risk management. Gates (2006), Liebenberg and Hoyt (2003) and Manab et al. (2010) also prove the influence of legal and regulatory compliance requirements such as the Sarbanes-Oxley Act. When it comes to the public sector, Anglo-Saxon countries contribute to a higher penetration of risk management in public administration. Though only in Australia at state level risk management finds legal precipitation and, in comparison to England and Canada, can be attributed to the biggest progress of risk management (Offerhaus, 2009). Australia, Canada and England developed generally accepted, non-obligatory standards for public organizations and, in addition with policy initiatives, have contributed to a spread of risk management (Offerhaus, 2009). Woods (2009) examines a UK city council and finds that the risk control system is contingent upon central government policies. Instead of a specific regulation on public sector risk management, the decision to implement risk management remains a local responsibility, but guidance and strong central government support for shared learning is provided.

Neo institutional theory supports the positive relationship between legal regulations and a municipality's implementation stage of risk management. When implementing risk management, an organisation complies with legal regulations, which grant legitimacy to an organisation (Eisenhardt, 1988). In consequence, we argue that guidelines about corporate governance or specific risk management regulations in Germany are an influencing force to the implementation of risk management in municipalities. This leads to the following research question:

RQ3. Do legal regulations on risk management affect the municipalities' stage of risk management implementation positively?

2.4 Risk management training

Education is an ongoing process and having qualified employees means training them in classroom instruction, self-study, or on-the-job to help keep pace and deal effectively with the evolving environment (COSO, 2004). Besides teaching particular risk issues, training seminars also provide important feedback to management on whether the risk management implemented is effective and indicate the participants risk and control consciousness (COSO, 2004). Farrugia (2002) argues that staff training is a key element in risk management and one that needs continuous reappraisal and regular courses to refresh skills. Pfister (2009) emphasizes the importance of constant training for control effectiveness and appropriate expertise of employees. Further studies find that inadequate training to the relevant staff hinders risk management implementation significantly (Gupta, 2011; Zhao et al., 2015). In this study, we expect that employees, who are actively trained in risk management, understand the risk management philosophy and process and are likely to more accurately identify threats to the organisation (Rae & Subramaniam, 2008). Agency theory supports the positive relationship between risk management training and the stage of risk management deployment. This is because monitoring activities of a principal – and thus agency costs – can be reduced by qualifying employees through training and further education in conjunction with risk management.

We argue that with a municipality offering risk management training, an employee's understanding of the importance and their commitment to risk management can be improved. Subsequently it can drive the implementation stage of risk management (Rae & Subramaniam, 2008). As a result, the following research question is raised:

RQ4. Is there a positive relationship between the extent of risk management training and the municipalities' stage of risk management implementation?

2.5 Employee fraud

As by definition of risk management, risks are potential events that threaten the achievements of the municipality's objectives. Fraud is one of the major risks and a component of operational risk that threatens a municipalities goals, their financial health, image and reputation (Doody, 2009). There are

different definitions of fraud, though in general it includes activities such as theft, corruption, embezzlement and others. The fraud triangle, first coined by Donald R. Cressey, shows the three factors incentive and opportunity to commit fraud as well as the rationalisation of the fraudster for justifying fraudulent behaviour (Albrecht et al., 1984). One example of a major fraud risk within municipalities is the risk of corruption and bribery in public procurement. Procurement regulations that include risk-retardant arrangements were implemented to prevent such fraud (Beck et al., 2013). Risk management is a management control system to identify and mitigate such risks. Moreover risk management is regarded as a key management control system to detect fraud (Parton et al., 2009). Out of an agency perspective, the occurrence of fraud leads to a need to close the information gaps and the associated defects between principal and agent and therefore can lead to a further developed risk management.

In this study, we examine if past fraud incidents within a municipality have led to a higher demand of an intact control environment and therefore to a further developed risk management. The subsequent research question is:

RQ5. Is there a positive relationship between past fraud incidences and the municipalities' stage of risk management implementation?

2.6 Resources

When it comes to implementing risk management, sufficient resources such as time are necessary. In their studies, Zhao et al. (2015) identify insufficient resources such as time to be the most critical hindrance to risk management implementation. Miccolis (2003) and KPMG (2010) find that companies list a lack of time as a barrier to successful risk management implementation. Thus, we argue that municipalities that face a lack of time are less advanced implementing risk management. Contingency theory underlies the assumption that internal and external factors can influence an organisations risk management. A shift of the internal factor resources such as the availability of time may cause a shift in an organisational stage of risk management implementation. Therefore, the research question is:

RQ6. Is there a positive relationship between the time available for implementing risk management and the municipalities' stage of risk management?

2.7 Quality

Based on COSO (2004) the organization's internal environment, its risk assessment policies and monitoring activities are seen to be distinct elements of a larger system of management controls. In consequence and adapted to the context of risk management in municipalities, the quality of measures and controls in risk management is assessed in key areas financial statements, operative municipality processes, strategy and compliance with laws, directives and standards. We assume that the quality of risk management is high when the four criteria are met. The criteria can be measured as follows.

- Financial statements require to be prepared reliably which means that the measurement methods are precisely applied and that reporting reflects the results correctly (Kinney, 2000).
- Operational municipal processes refers to the executive and management to have reasonable assurance that the operational objectives are achieved (Pfister, 2009).
- Strategy objectives are usually set by the executive and represent the municipality's main topics for the upcoming years.
- Compliance with laws, directives and standards is reached when records meet the external regulatory requirements as well as internal policies (Kinney, 2000).

In this study, we expect that municipalities with further developed risk management are more likely to have a high-quality risk management.

RQ7. Is there a positive relationship between the municipalities' stage of risk management implementation and the quality of risk management?

2.8 The moderating role of an organisations size

The organisation size is a classical contingent factor used in existing contingency theory. Researchers find that large organisations tend to use more formal control systems employing specialists (e.g. Colquitt et al., 1999; Beasley et al., 2005; Hoyt et al., 2001). Woods (2009) confirms in her work assessing a case study in public administration that larger organisations have higher formality. Higher formality is characterised by a tendency towards a high number of specialists using sophisticated technologies and heavily documented control systems. Further Gordon et al. (2009), Beasley et al.

(2005), Hoyt and Liebenberg (2011) and Zhao et al. (2015) find firm size to be an important factor to the adoption of risk management. They find that larger organisations are more likely to implement risk management because of higher complexity facing a wider range of risks and having more resources made available to support risk management implementation.

Thus we anticipate that larger organisations would be more likely to adopt risk management due to the need for a comprehensive risk management strategy (Kleffner et al., 2003). In consequence, we examine the influence of factors on risk management implementation between large and small municipalities and apply the municipality’s size as a moderating factor which leads us to the following exploratory research question:

RQ8. Do executive support, competence, legal regulations, risk management training, employee fraud and resources take a stronger influence on the stage of risk management in large municipalities than in small municipalities?

The development of research questions subsequently forms the research model as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Research model

3 Research method

As a pre-stage to the empirical study, the relevant literature was analysed, which represents the theoretical basis for the derivation of this research methodology (Weischer, 2007). The subsequent analysis process is explained by the sample and data collection, followed by the data analysis and variable measurement. To assess the effects of the research model, an empirical study with a quantitative survey was chosen. The research model is tested using partial least squares path modelling with the Smart PLS Version 3 Software.

3.1 Sample and data collection

Data collection was undertaken through a questionnaire survey distributed to mainly the person responsible for risk management, which is generally represented by the Head of Finance or Head of Administration in German municipalities. The selection criteria of the sample were: (i) a population of more than 1,000, which ensures that a minimum level of formalized risk management structures can be expected of those municipalities that take part in the study; (ii) municipal administrations, city councils and administration communities were included, except owner-operated municipal enterprises and municipal companies. Taking into account these selection criteria, a gross sample (Piehler, 2011) of 1,500 municipalities was chosen. Out of this gross sample a representative stratified probability sample was selected. A last important selection criterion was (iii) the availability of an e-mail address due to the web-based survey method. If more than one municipality that is operated by the same administration communities was selected, the unit was contacted only once. At the end of the evaluation process, the adjusted gross sample (Piehler, 2011) of 1,383 German municipalities was found which met the selection criteria.

Empirical data was collected through a web-based questionnaire. To check the questionnaire's relevance and the constructs (Dillman, 2007) it was pre-tested with a small group of academics and

persons responsible for risk management in German municipalities.¹ This resulted in some modifications to the wording and in the presentation of the questionnaire.

The first e-mail was sent to participants in April 2015. To increase the response rate a reminder was sent after 11 days and a second reminder after another 16 days to non-responders. A total of 227 participants from 1,383 were received (16.4 per cent response rate), of which 209 were useable (15.1 per cent) and completely finished the survey. The final sample is 209 organisations, which is distributed to the size range as shown in Table 1.

Number of inhabitants	Gross sample (number of respondents per group / gross sample per group)	Number of respondents (number of respondents per group / total number of respondents)
1,000 to 2,000	406 (3 %)	12 (6%)
2,000 to 4,999	480 (12 %)	56 (27%)
5,000 to 9,999	282 (16 %)	44 (21%)
10,000 to 19,999	187 (28 %)	52 (25%)
20,000 to 49,999	106 (26 %)	27 (13%)
50,000 to 99,999	23 (22 %)	5 (2%)
More than 100,000	16 (80 %)	13 (6%)
<i>Total</i>	<i>1500</i>	<i>209 (100 %)</i>

Table 1 Sample respondents by number of inhabitants

The data was checked for potential causes of possible systematic measurement errors. Particularly the measurement errors common method variance², key informant bias³, non-response bias⁴ and non-representativeness⁵ were considered. The four methods showed no problematic results and the data quality can therefore be regarded as good.

¹ Three professors and three research associates of Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts, one professor of the University of Siegen and three people in the audience of the main study tested the questionnaire on clarity, completeness and acceptance.

² To prevent error sources such as a distortion of the response due to Item-Context, Item-Characteristic, and survey context, specific aspects were considered. To prevent method distortion due to single source bias, a Harman's-One-Factor test was undertaken. Based on the results it is concluded that no substantial method distortion exists.

³ With 87% of the participants in the position of Head of Finance and 7% being Head of Administration it can be concluded that the survey participants are informants.

⁴ The assessment of non-response bias was undertaken by a two-sided t-test, splitting the sample into two groups: respondents before (survey period day 1 to 11) and after the first reminder (survey period day 12 to 27). The result shows no significant differences at the 10% significance level.

⁵ To test the sample for representativeness, meaning that it does not significantly differ to its population, the sample was tested for strong over- or underrepresentation of a municipality size. While small municipalities

3.2 Data analysis

Data from the survey is used to test our model which is calculated with the partial least squares approach to structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM). The PLS path modelling used was developed by Wold (1982) and its algorithm is modified as suggested by Lohmöller (1989). The reason for using this technique is because it is appropriate to the exploratory nature of this study where the latent variables used are still in development or have not yet been tested in the circumstances of a public administration (Ainuddin et al., 2007). Two reflective multi-item measurement models comprise the relationship between the latent variable and with its respective manifest variables. Four variables are measured using a single-item measurement. The structural model embodies the relationships between the independent variables and the implementation stage of risk management measuring the influence on the implementation stage of risk management in a municipality. Further, the implementation stage of risk management is tested for its influence in risk management quality, as shown in Fig. 1. The PLS-SEM is tested in a two-stage approach, first assessing the reflective measurement model and secondly testing the structural model for its research questions. Organisational size is included in the PLS model as a moderating variable. To verify the moderating effect, a multi group analysis that compares differences of path coefficients and its significance of two or more groups of data is used (Henseler & Fassott, 2010). The PLS multi group analysis applied bases on the method introduced by Henseler et al. (2009).

3.3 Variable measurement

Executive support is assessed asking the respondents to what extent the executive demands a systematic and active risk management. The variable is measured using a five-point Likert-type scale where “1” represents no executive support at all and “5” represents very strong executive support.

Competence in dealing with risk is measured using a three item, five-point Likert-type scale (1 - totally disagree to 5 - totally agree). Indicators are adopted in a modified form from theory (Pfister, 2009;

rather are underrepresented compared to the population (27% of population chosen, 6% of net sample participated), big municipalities (cities) rather are overrepresented (1% of population chosen, 6% of net sample participated). This distribution can be explained since smaller municipalities are less concerned with the formal and documented risk management and in consequence responded less frequently. Another argument is found in the elimination of municipalities administrated in communities (small municipalities), which meant that one person represented several samples.

COSO, 1992; COSO, 2013; Zhao et al., 2015). The respondents were asked to indicate such as “The professional competence of the employees participating in the handling of risk seems very high to me” or “The employees are very familiar with the risks and controls in their areas of competence”.

Legal regulations are measured using a dichotomous (yes/no) scale where “0” represents no legal obligation to implementing risk management and “1” represents legal obligation to implementing risk management.

Risk management training is measured by asking the respondents if administration offers employees to attend in risk management training (e.g. internal or external training courses, seminars, workshops) with a yes/no scale. The indicator is derived from Rae and Subramaniam (2008) who examine the association between the quality of internal control and the degree of education and training in risk management. The indicator though has to be adapted to the present circumstances.

Employee fraud is measured using a dichotomous (yes/no) scale where “0” represents no employee fraud, and “1” represents one or more instances of employee fraud (Rae & Subramaniam, 2008). Respondents were asked if fraud was uncovered in the past within the municipal administration.

Resources are assessed with the indicator time where participants were required to rate the factor time as a hindrance to risk management implementation. A five-point Likert-type scale is used between “1” being to a large extent to “5” representing strongly disagree.

Stage of risk management implementation is measured using a five-point Likert-type scale based on the measurement instrument as used by Beasley et al. (2005) and reflects a value ranging from 1 to 5 (see Table 2). Stages one to three are considered risk management implementers (35%) while stages four to five are considered non-implementers (65%).

<i>Implementation stage of risk management</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
1 An over all areas fully documented and monitored risk management is introduced.	1	0.5
2 An over all areas fully documented risk management is introduced, but it is not monitored regularly.	4	1.9
3 A partially documented risk management is introduced (e.g. only certain areas of risk covered).	68	32.5
4 No documented risk management exists, however it has been decided to establish a risk management over the next few years.	22	10.5
5 No documented risk management exists and it is not intended to establish a risk management over the next few years.	114	54.5
<i>Total</i>	<i>209</i>	<i>100</i>

Table 2 Risk management implementation stages

Quality of risk management is assessed based on a four-item, five-point Likert-type scale, where each participant was required to rate the quality of their measures and controls in risk management in four key areas of the municipality. These included “financial statements”, “operative municipality processes”, “strategy” and “compliance with laws, directives and standards”. A five-point Likert-type scale anchors at both ends where 1 – very poor to 5 – very good is utilised.

The moderating role of the organisational size. Basically, a moderator can be determined as a variable “that effects the direction and/or strength of the relation between an independent [...] and a dependent or criterion variable” (Baron & Kenny, 1986). A moderator effect exists when a path coefficient is significantly affected by one or more variables (Hair et al., 2014). If a particular path coefficient is more pronounced at high moderator values than at low values, there exists a positive moderating effect and vice versa (Giering, 2000). Organisational size is most commonly measured by using the indicator of the number of employees (Chenhall, 2003) as it is measured in this work. Consequently, respondents were asked for the number of employees of the organisation equivalent to full time. To analyse the moderator effects, the data is split into a group with small municipalities and a group of large municipalities by its median (Henseler & Fassott, 2010). The median results in the amount of 50 employees’ equivalent to full time. 105 municipalities are considered as large municipalities having 50 and more employees’ equivalent to full time, while the remaining 104 municipalities are combined into the group of small municipalities.

4 Results

This section describes the results of the reflective measurement models that are assessed in a first step followed by the appraisal of the structural model to test the research questions in the second step. It is thirdly followed by the test of the moderator organisational size. The assessment of the reflective measurement model is only applicable to multi-item constructs, which applies to the constructs competence and quality. The results to the research model, depicted in Fig. 2, include the reflective measurement models and the structural model.

Fig. 2 Parameter estimates of PLS analysis

4.1 Assessment of the reflective measurement model

4.1.1 Reliability analysis

To analyse the reliability of a construct, the Cronbach's Alpha is used as the most common measure (Churchill, 1979). It assesses the average value of all correlation combinations of individual indicators of a construct and takes values between zero and one (Hair et al., 2014). In literature, often the lower limit of 0.7 for established constructs (Nunnally, 1978) or 0.6 for newly developed constructs are used (Malhotra, 1993). Table 3 shows that the Cronbach's Alpha values ranges from 0.741 to 0.833 and therefore exceed the cut off values of 0.7 as suggested by Nunnally (1978).

Latent variable	Manifest variable	Loadings	t-statistic	α	CR	AVE
Competence	Item 1	0.908	52.35	0.833	0.894	0.74
	Item 2	0.915	45.90			
	Item 3	0.746	10.26			
Quality	Item 1	0.764	14.57	0.741	0.838	0.568
	Item 2	0.864	24.69			
	Item 3	0.754	14.40			
	Item 4	0.612	7.190			

AVE represents average variance extracted, α represents Cronbach's Alpha, CR represents composite reliability.

Table 3 Parameter estimates of measurement model

Another measure for testing the reliability of a measurement model is referred to as composite reliability. It is preferred over Cronbach's alpha due to its limitation indicating that all items are equally weighted. Composite reliability takes into consideration that indicators may have different factor loadings (Hair et al., 2014). Literature recommends a threshold value of 0.6 (Nunnally, 1978), which in both cases with a value of more than 0.8 can be regarded as satisfactory.

Further, reliability can be verified by the measure indicator reliability. It is a measure for estimating the variation of an item that is explained by the construct. Indicator reliability is evaluated by the square of a standardized indicator's outer loading (Hair et al., 2014). It takes values between zero and one, whereas literature recommends a minimal acceptable value of 0.3 (Homburg, 1992). By the use of the t-value it can be assessed if a factor loading differs significantly from zero and has subsequently to be eliminated (Bagozzi et al., 1991). With item 4 of the latent variable quality having the lowest value that is within the minimal accepted value of 0.3 and all of them being significant, there is no need for eliminating an item. The results provide support to conclude that the measurements for both latent variables are reliable and show a sufficient quality for the usage in the structural model.

4.1.2 Convergent validity

Subsequent to the reliability measure, convergent validity can be derived by the estimation of standardised loadings and average variance extracted (AVE). Convergent validity examines the degree of matching of different measurements of the same construct considering alternative indicators. A high

outer loading is reached, if the indicators of latent variables are highly correlated with each other (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988). The square of standardised loadings measures the proportion of the variation in an item that is explained by the construct. Ideally, more than 50 % of each indicators variance should be explained by a latent variable, which corresponds to factor loading higher than 0.708 (Hair et al., 2014).

Table 3 shows that the standardized loadings are above the cut-off value of 0.708 except for the variable quality item 4. With a value of 0.612 though it still reaches a satisfactory loading which especially is accepted when newly developed scales are used (Hulland, 1999). Finally, the model can be examined by the figure of AVE, which indicates what percentage of the total variance of the indicators is explained by the estimated construct. It's threshold value is at 0.5 or higher (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988). The values of competence and quality are above the recommended value which indicates that more than half of the variance of its indicators is explained.

4.1.3 Discriminant validity

The discriminant validity expresses whether and to what extent the various constructs are distinct from each other. The discriminant validity can be calculated using the Fornell and Larcker criterion (Jöreskog & Sörbom, 1982). The criterion analyses whether or not AVE is greater than the square correlations of the variables (Hair et al., 2014).

Latent variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Executive support	n.a.							
2. Competence	0.066	0.740						
3. Legal regulations	0.004	0.000	n.a.					
4. Risk management training	0.056	0.043	0.026	n.a.				
5. Employee fraud	0.001	0.003	0.001	0.001	n.a.			
6. Resources	0.007	0.017	0.000	0.020	0.000	n.a.		
7. Quality	0.092	0.164	0.001	0.035	0.008	0.007	0.568	
8. Status Quo	0.056	0.094	0.106	0.162	0.026	0.041	0.093	n.a.

Diagonals (in bold) represent the AVE while off diagonals represent squared correlations of factor pairs. AVEs for single-items constructs are not available (n.a.).

Table 4 Discriminant validity of constructs

The AVE of competence (0.74) and quality (0.568) are greater than the highest squared correlation with any other construct or variable (0.164 for both competence and quality) wherefore the discriminant validity is guaranteed, as shown in Table 4. Overall, the results deriving from the structural model provide adequate convergent- and discriminant validity and reliability. The next step addresses the assessment of the structural model to answer the research questions.

4.2 Assessment of structural model for testing the research questions

While the confirmation of the construct measures focuses on the two constructs competence and quality, the assessment of the structural model to test the research questions focuses on both, multi- as well as single-item constructs. The use of single-item measures has been legitimated in literature and the capability of it as a potential viable alternative to multi-item scales for construct measurement purposes have been demonstrated (Bergkvist & Rossiter, 2007; Drolet & Morrison, 2001). Fuchs and Diamantopoulos (2009) developed a framework within which single-item measures can be evaluated for acceptability. The single-items used in this work are tested for these criteria and assessed to be valid measures to be used in the structural model.

4.2.1 Path coefficients

A path coefficient's magnitude indicates the relationships among the latent variables. The values range from -1 to 1, where the higher the number the stronger positive is the relationship and vice versa for negative values (Hair et al., 2014). Path coefficients, which must be significantly different from zero should have values ≥ 0.1 (Lohmöller, 1989). Table 6 shows that all path coefficients exceed 0.1 and therefore have a fairly strong positive relationship within the model.

Research question	Path	Path coefficients	Standard error	t-statistic	VIF
1	Executive support → Status Quo	0.118*	0.062	1.900	1.128
2	Competence → Status Quo	0.213****	0.057	3.727	1.111
3	Legal regulations → Status Quo	0.283****	0.060	4.717	1.041
4	Risk management training → Status Quo	0.271****	0.065	4.136	1.138
5	Employee fraud → Status Quo	0.167***	0.059	2.830	1.008
6	Resources → Status Quo	0.127**	0.060	2.122	1.033
7	Status Quo → Quality	0.306****	0.053	5.753	

Legend (two tailed):
 * 10 %-level (t-value ≥ 1.645)
 ** 5 %-level (t-value ≥ 1.960)
 *** 1 %-level (t-value ≥ 2.575)
 **** 0.1 %-level (t-value ≥ 3.291)

Table 5 Bootstrap summary of research model and results

The significance of the path coefficient is measured using the t-statistic. For this, the standard error, to determine whether a coefficient is significant, is calculated by the means of bootstrapping. The values shown in Table 5 are computed through bootstrapping procedure applying a two-tailed test with 5,000 samples without sign changes, using the Bias-Corrected and accelerated bootstrap confidence interval method and parallel processing. The bootstrapping procedure applied relies on a non-parametric test as suggested by Chin (1998). This is because PLS-SEM does not assume that the data is normally distributed (Hair et al., 2014). T-values ≥ 3.291 (significance level of 0.1), ≥ 2.575 (significance level of 1), ≥ 1.960 (significance level of 5) or ≥ 1.645 (significance level of 10) indicate a significant indicator weight. Legal regulations (0.283****) contributes most to the development stage of risk management followed in decreasing order by risk management training (0.271****), competence

(0.213****), employee fraud (0.167***), resources (0.127**) and executive support (0.118*). The path coefficients as shown in Table 5 such as competence, legal regulations and risk management training linking to the development stage of risk management (Status Quo) as well as the development stage of risk management linking to the quality of risk management are significant at 0.1 per cent level. Employee fraud is significant at 1 per cent level, resources at 5 per cent level and executive support is significant at 10 per cent level linking to the development stage of risk management.

These results so far answer the research questions 1-7 positively. It indicates legal regulations as the most influential predictor with a positive and significant effect on the implementation level of risk management. Risk management training and competence are very influential predictors with high significance.

4.2.2 *Coefficient of determination and effect size*

Besides the path coefficients and the correlation of the paths, further criteria needs to be tested when assessing the structural model. The criteria include coefficient of determination (R^2) and effect size (f^2) (Hair et al., 2014).

The coefficient of determination reflects the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is predictable from the independent variable. The more the result reaches towards 1, the better the predictive accuracy is (Henseler et al., 2009). Coefficients of determination of ≥ 0.67 can be assessed as solid, ≥ 0.33 as average and < 0.19 as weak (Chin, 1998). However, these values are put into perspective depending on the research context (Hair et al., 2014). The six variables explain 34.7 % of the variance of the implementation stage of risk management, which is an indication for an adequate predictive power of the model. Instead, the coefficient of determination explaining the quality of risk management is with almost 10 % rather low.

Independent variable	Dependent variable	R ²	f ²
Executive support	Status Quo	0.347	0.019
Competence			0.062
Legal regulations			0.118
Risk management training			0.099
Employee fraud			0.043
Resources			0.024

R² represents the coefficient of determination, f² represents the effect size.

Table 6 Coefficient of determination (R²) and effect size (f²)

Another quality criterion is the effect size measuring the change of the coefficient determination, if a latent variable in the analysis of the structural equation model is eliminated (Lohmöller, 1989). Values are demanded of ≥ 0.02 for an impact of the model (Chin, 1998). Hence, Table 6 shows that an impact is detected for all the effect sizes.

4.3 Assessment of size as a moderating effect

To understand the moderating effect of an organisations size towards the Status Quo of risk management and the quality of risk management, this study measured the model splitting the sample into two groups by its median.

As a prerequisite for the implementation of a multi-group analysis, the equality of factor loadings of the reflective measurement models must be assessed in both groups by means of the Coefficient of Congruence (CoC). This is so that any differences of path coefficients identified are meaningful interpretable (Carte & Russell, 2003). The CoC may take values between 0 and 1, whereas a level of at least 0.9 indicates an identical factor loading structure (Teel & Verran, 1991). The test results indicate that all reflective measurement models have a sufficient CoC of ≥ 0.9 and therefore a nearly identical factor loading structure. The assessment of the models “small municipality” and “large municipality” reveal reliable and valid measurements.

In Table 7 the path coefficients of the two groups, the corresponding t-values, effect sizes and the path differences between the two subgroups are reported. The values are computed through bootstrapping

procedure applying a two-tailed test with 5,000 samples. Whether a research question is answered positively or negatively is determined by the path difference and their significance in the right column.

The results indicate that specifically the driver executive support has lower influence on the stage of risk management implementation in small municipalities than in larger municipalities and the path coefficient significantly differs. It is worth noting that the driver executive support has no relevant effect on the implementation stage of risk management in small municipalities. In contrast, its importance increases significantly for large organisations (path coefficient 0.243**) compared with the main model (path coefficient 0.118*). The driver Status Quo meaning a municipality's stage of risk management implementation has a significant higher influence on quality of risk management in large municipalities (0.417****) than in small municipalities (0.229***).

In contrary, the driver legal regulations has a higher influence on risk management implementation in a small municipality than in a large municipality. With a path coefficient of 0.331**** the driver legal regulations takes the biggest influence on a small municipalities status in implementing risk management. Though with a path coefficient of 0.219** the driver legal regulations is still significant to large municipalities. Employee fraud and resources play a fairly important role in small municipalities, whereas the variable resources for both small (path coefficient 0.123 n.s.) and large (path coefficient 0.068 n.s.) organisations takes a smaller influence than in the main model (path coefficient 0.127**). The driver resource has no relevant effect on the implementation stage of risk management in large municipalities.

The variables competence and risk management training take a similar influence on the implementation stage of risk management at small and large municipalities. In consequence, only executive support and quality of risk management take significant different influence on small and large municipalities.

Path	Path coefficients		T-statistic		Effect size f^2		Path difference
	small	large	small	large	small	large	
Executive support -> Status Quo	0.015	0.243	0.192	2.504	0.000	0.072	0.228*
Competence -> Status Quo	0.237	0.200	3.106	2.056	0.081	0.051	-0.037 (n.s.)
Legal regulations -> Status Quo	0.331	0.219	3.702	2.356	0.170	0.069	-0.112 (n.s.)
Risk management training -> Status Quo	0.269	0.260	2.909	2.930	0.099	0.089	-0.010 (n.s.)
Employee fraud -> Status Quo	0.179	0.101	1.902	1.201	0.048	0.014	-0.078 (n.s.)
Resources -> Status Quo	0.123	0.068	1.313	0.804	0.024	0.006	-0.055 (n.s.)
Status Quo -> Quality	0.229	0.417	3.084	5.855	0.056	0.211	-0.188*

Legend:
n.s. not significant
* 10%-level (t-value > 1.645)

Table 7 Testing research questions for the moderator effect size

5 Discussion and limitations

Having examined the data and research questions in the previous section, this part provides further insight into the relationships of different variables affecting the implementation stage of risk management and its quality and putting the factors in context of its theoretical foundation.

The mean analysis of the latent variables shows that the factor legal regulations is critical to extensive risk management deployment in German municipalities. This result suggests that if a municipality must comply with legal and regulatory requirements relating to risk management, it is more likely to have a further advanced risk management development status. This result is in line with Kleffner et al. (2003), Gates (2006), Liebenberg and Hoyt (2003), Manab et al. (2010) and Zhao et al. (2015) who prove the influence of legal and regulatory compliance requirements.

In additional analysis, we find a moderating effect for the support of the executive when implementing risk management having a significantly stronger effect in large municipalities. In practice, this implies that as the municipality becomes bigger, the council starts playing a more important role towards risk management taking their responsibility towards good corporate governance. Sobel and Reding (2004), Kleffner et al. (2003) and Beasley et al. (2005) show comparable results as they underline an executive's role as being a main factor that affects the adoption of risk management.

Risk management training has a statistical significant effect on the implementation stage of risk management. The results demonstrate that employees can be encouraged to develop risk management

if provided by appropriate knowledge and more extensive training on risk management. The many organizational and technical barriers that are to overcome when implementing risk management (Miccolis 2003) emphasize that an investment to obtain qualified personnel and expertise within the municipality is necessary.

In line with results found by Rae and Subramaniam (2008), we find a positive effect on employee fraud towards the implementation stage of risk management. Out of 209 studied municipalities, 23 % (n = 48) uncovered cases of fraud within their municipality in the past. Further the survey shows that the larger the municipality the bigger is the percentage of uncovered cases of fraud, as shown in Table 8.

Population	less than 2,000	up to 5,000	up to 10,000	up to 20,000	up to 50,000	up to 100,000	more than 100,000
Cases of fraud uncovered	2	5	12	12	8	2	7
Total replies	12	56	44	52	27	5	13
Percentage	16.7	8.9	27.3	23.1	29.6	40.0	53.8

Table 8 Cases of fraud uncovered in the past in German municipalities

The results highlight to managers and executives the importance of providing adequate resources such as sufficient time for employees to implement and develop a risk management within a municipality. Further, the results answer RQ7 having a positive interaction between implementation stage of risk management and the quality of risk management. These results support the findings of Rae and Subramaniam (2008) who investigate in privately owned companies and show that the results can be adapted to the context of risk management in municipalities. The results of the multi-group analysis to answer RQ 8 suggest that the stage of risk management implementation is both significant in small and large municipalities, though it has a significant stronger effect in large municipalities. This indicates that large municipalities that implemented risk management may designate to a high quality risk management and are able to depict their complexity and the wider range of risks, as suggested by Gordon et al. (2009), Beasley et al. (2005), Hoyt and Liebenberg (2011) and Zhao et al. (2015).

In this study, the variability in the stage of risk management in German municipalities is explained by both internal (i.e. executive support, competence, risk management training, employee fraud and

resources) and external (i.e. legal regulations) factors. Agency theory was used to identify internal factors, suggesting that risk management may reduce uncertainty and information asymmetry through its monitoring function. Neo institutional theory postulates that risk management is adopted to meet external pressure such as legal regulations. Overall, both proved to be fruitful foundations to derive relevant factors for risk management implementation in German municipalities.

In conclusion, this study adds to the risk management literature in three ways. It presents that certain factors proven to influence the state of risk management in privately owned companies can be adapted to the context of municipalities. Further the results demonstrate that besides regulations also other variables can support risk management implementation. An understanding of these forces assists various stakeholders to know where to obtain support and how to strengthen positive influences for an advanced stage of risk management implementation. An advanced stage of risk management implementation finally helps stakeholders to ensure that public funds are used appropriately, to improve transparency, and even increase performance for a better fulfilment of municipalities' responsibilities. The results assist various stakeholders interested to better reach these aims and allow strengthening the positive influence. Cases of fraud have made many municipalities realise that an implemented risk management might help to prevent further cases of fraud.

Despite the achievement of the objectives, we acknowledge the limitations in our research approach. First, the variables identified in this study may not continue to hold true over time. Secondly, as the findings are interpreted in the context of German municipalities, there may be geographical limitation on the identification of the variables to risk management implementation.

The findings of this study serve as a foundation for future studies on risk management in the public sector. Thus, this study contributes to the still very limited knowledge relating to public sector risk management. Future research would investigate the current stage of public sector risk management in different countries and disclose the relationship of a variance of variables that affect the stage of risk management development and its quality in different countries.

References

- Ainuddin, R. A., Beamish, P. W., Hulland, J. S., & Rouse, M. J. (2007). Resource attributes and firm performance in international joint ventures. *Journal of World Business, 42*(1), 47–60.
- Albrecht, W. S., Howe, K. R., & Romney, M. B. (1984). *Deterring fraud: The internal auditor's perspective*. Altamonte Springs, Fla.: Institute of Internal Auditors Research Foundation.
- Arwinge, O. (2013). *Internal control: A study of concept and themes*. Heidelberg, New York: Physica-Verlag.
- Bagozzi, R., Yi, Y., & Philipps, L. (1991). Assessing Construct Validity in Organizational Research. *Administrative Science Quarterly, 36*(3), 421–458.
- Bagozzi, R. P., & Yi, Y. (1988). On the evaluation of structural equation models. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science, 16*(1), 74–94.
- Baron, R. M., & Kenny, D. A. (1986). The Moderator-Mediator Variable Distinction in Social Psychological Research: Conceptual, Strategic, and Statistical Considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 51*(6), 1173–1182.
- Beasley, M. S., Clune, R., & Hermanson, D. R. (2005). Enterprise risk management: An empirical analysis of factors associated with the extent of implementation. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy, 24*(6), 521–531.
- Beck, S., Benecke, M., Felten, M., Lipske, U., & Schuster, F. (2013). *Risikomanagement in Kommunen* (Public Governance. Zeitschrift für öffentliches Management). Retrieved from http://www.publicgovernance.de/docs/PG-Sommer_2013_Risikomanagement_in_Kommunen.pdf
- Bergkvist, L., & Rossiter, J. R. (2007). The Predictive Validity of Multiple-Item Versus Single-Item Measures of the Same Constructs. *Journal of Marketing Research, 44*(2), 175–184.
- Burger, A., & Schmelter, H. (2012). *Internal Control für Führungskräfte*. München: Oldenbourg.
- Carte, T. A., & Russell, C. J. (2003). In pursuit of moderation: Nine common errors and their solutions. *MIS Quarterly, 27*(3), 479–501.
- Chenhall, R. H. (2003). Management control systems design within its organizational context: findings from contingency-based research and directions for the future. *Accounting, Organizations and Society, 28*(2–3), 127–168.
- Chin, W. W. (1998). The partial least square approach for structural equation modeling. In G. A. Marcoulides (Ed.), *Modern methods for business research* (pp. 295–336). Mahwah: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Churchill, G. A. (1979). A paradigm for developing better measures of marketing constructs. *Journal of Marketing Research, 16*(1), 64–73.
- Colquitt, L. L., Hoyt, R. E., & Lee, R. B. (1999). Integrated Risk Management and the Role of the Risk Manager. *Risk Management and Insurance Review, 2*(3), 43–61. doi:10.1111/j.1540-6296.1999.tb00003.x
- COSO. (1992). *Internal Control - Integrated Framework* (Vol. I). Jersey City: Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission.
- COSO. (2004). Enterprise Risk Management—Integrated Framework. Retrieved from www.coso.org
- COSO. (2013). *Internal Control - INtegrated Framework. Framework and Appendices*. Jersey City: Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission.

- Daud, W., Haron, H., & Ibrahim, D. (2011). The Role of Quality Board of Directors in Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) Practices: Evidence from Binary Logistic Regression. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 6(12), 205–211. doi:10.1080/135184798337317
- Dillman, D. A. (2007). *Mail and Internet surveys: The tailored design method: 2007 update with new internet, visual and mixed-mode guide* (2nd ed.). Hoboken: John Wiley.
- Domokos, L., Nyeki, M., Jakovac, K., Nemeth, E., & Hatvani, C. (2015). Risk Analysis and Risk Management in the Public Sector and in Public Auditing. *Public Finance Quaterly*. (1), 7–28.
- Doody, H. (2009). *Fraud risk management: A guide to good practice*. London: CIMA.
- Drolet, A. L., & Morrison, D. G. (2001). Do we really need multiple-item measures in service research? *Journal of Service Research*, 3(3), 196–204.
- Eisenhardt, K. M. (1988). Agency- and Institutional-Theory Explanations: The Case of Retail Sales Compensation. *Academy of Management Journal*, 31(3), 488–544.
- Eisenring, C. (2014). Berliner Pünktlichkeit. Retrieved from <http://www.nzz.ch/wirtschaft/berliner-puenktlichkeit-1.18444577>
- Fama, E. F., & Jensen, M. C. (1983). Separation of ownership and control. *Journal of Law and Economics*, 26(2), 301–325.
- Farrugia, S. (2002). A dangerous occupation? Violence in public libraries. *New Library World*, 103(9), 309–319.
- Fone, M., & Young, P. C. (2000). *Public sector risk management*. Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann.
- Fuchs, C., & Diamantopoulos, A. (2009). Using single-item measures for construct measurement in management research. *Die Betriebswirtschaft*, 69(2), 195–210.
- Gates, S. (2006). Incorporating Strategic Risk into Enterprise Risk Management: A Survey of Current Corporate Practice. *Journal of Applied Corporate Finance*, 18(4), 81–90.
- Giering, A. (2000). *Der Zusammenhang zwischen Kundenzufriedenheit und Kundenloyalität: Eine Untersuchung moderierender Effekte*. Wiesbaden: Gabler.
- Gordon, L. A., Loeb, M. P., & Tseng, C.-Y. (2009). Enterprise risk management and firm performance: A contingency perspective. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 28(4), 301. Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com/docview/214417953?accountid=15920>
- Gupta, P. K. (2011). Risk management in Indian companies: EWRM concerns and issues. *The Journal of Risk Finance*, 12(2), 121–139.
- Gemeindeordnung für den Freistaat Bayern, GVBl 1998.
- Hair, J., Hult, T., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2014). *A primer on partial least squares structural equations modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Los Angeles: SAGE.
- Hampton, J. J. (2015). *Fundamentals of enterprise risk management: How top companies assess risk, manage exposure, and seize opportunity* (2nd ed.). New York: American Management Association.
- Henseler, J., & Fassott, G. (2010). Testing Moderating Effects in PLS Path Models: An Illustration of Available Procedures. In V. E. Vinzi, W. W. Chin, J. Henseler, & H. Wang (Eds.), *Handbook of partial least squares* (pp. 713–735). Berlin et al.: Springer.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sinkovics, R. R. (2009). The Use of Partial Least Squares Path Modeling in International Marketing. In Sinkovics, R. R: Ghauri, P. N (Ed.), *Advances in International Marketing* (pp. 277–320). Bingley: Emerald.
- Homburg, C. (1992). Die Kausalanalyse – Eine Einführung. *Wirtschaftswissenschaftliches Studium*, 21(10), 499–508.
- Hoyt, R. E., & Liebenberg, A. P. (2011). The value of enterprise risk management. *Journal of Risk and Insurance*, 78(4), 795–822.

- Hoyt, R. E., Merkley, B., & Thiessen, K. (2001). *A Composite Sketch of a Chief Risk Officer*. Toronto: The Conference Board of Canada.
- Hulland, J. (1999). Use of partial least squares (PLS) in strategic management research: A review of four recent studies. *Strategic Management Journal*, 20(2), 195.
- IFAC. (2013). Evaluating and Improving Internal Control in Organizations. Retrieved from <http://www.ifac.org/publications-resources/evaluating-and-improving-internal-control-organizations-0>
- International Organisation for Standardisation. (2009). ISO 31000:2009. Risk management—Principles and guidelines. Retrieved from <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:31000:ed-1:v1:en>
- Jöreskog, K., & Sörbom, D. (1982). Recent Developments in Structural Equation Modeling. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 19(4), 404–416.
- Kinney, W. R. (2000). *Information quality assurance and internal control for management decision making*. Boston: Irwin/McGraw-Hill.
- Kleffner, A. E., Lee, R. B., & McGannon, B. (2003). The effect of corporate governance of the use of enterprise risk management: Evidence from Canada. *Risk Management and Insurance Review*, 6(1), 53–73.
- KPMG. (2010). Charting a safe and sustainable growth journey: Singapore Enterprise Risk Management Survey 2010. Retrieved from <https://www.kpmg.com/SG/en/IssuesAndInsights/ArticlesPublications/Documents/SgERMSurvey2010.pdf>
- Liebenberg, A. P., & Hoyt, R. E. (2003). The determinants of enterprise risk management: Evidence from the appointment of chief risk officers. *Risk Management and Insurance Review*, 6(1), 37–52.
- Lohmöller, J.-B. (1989). *Latent variable path modeling with partial least squares*. Heidelberg: Physica-Verlag.
- Malhotra, N. K. (1993). *Marketing research: An applied orientation*. Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall.
- Manab, N., Kassim, I., & Hussin, M. (2010). Enterprise-Wide Risk Management (EWRM) Practices: Between Corporate Governance Compliance and Value Creation. *International Review of Business Research Papers*, 6(2), 239–252.
- Marchetti, A. M. (2012). *Enterprise risk management best practices: From assessment to ongoing compliance*. Wiley corporate F & A series. Hoboken, N.J.: Wiley.
- Meyer, J. W., & Rowan, B. (1977). Institutionalized Organizations: Formal Structure as Myth and Ceremony. *American Journal of Sociology*, 83(2), 340–363.
- Miccolis, J. (2003). ERM Lessons Across Industries. Retrieved from <http://www.irmi.com/expert/articles/2003/miccolis03.aspx>
- Nunnally, J. C. (1978). *Psychometric theory*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Offerhaus, J. (2009). Risikomanagement der Öffentlichen Hand – Erfahrungen aus den angelsächsischen Ländern. In F. Scholz, A. Schuler, & H.-P. Schwintowski (Eds.), *Risikomanagement der Öffentlichen Hand* (pp. 79–116). Physica-Verlag HD.
- Parton, T., Rajarao, V., & Skalak, S. (2009). The Global Economic Crime Survey. Retrieved from https://www.pwc.ch/user_content/editor/files/publ_adv/pwc_global_economic_crime_survey_09_e.pdf
- Pfister, J. A. (2009). *Managing organizational culture for effective internal control: From practice to theory*. Contributions to management science. Berlin: Berlin : Physica-Verlag. Retrieved from http://sfx.ethz.ch/sfx_locator?sid=ALEPH:EBI01&genre=book&isbn=3790823392
- Piehler, R. (2011). *Interne Markenführung: Theoretisches Konzept und fallstudienbasierte Evidenz*. Wiesbaden: Gabler.

- Rae, K., & Subramaniam, N. (2008). Quality of internal control procedures. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 23(2), 104–124.
- RiskNET. (2014). Fehlanzeige: Risikomanagement in Kommunen. Retrieved from <https://www.risknet.de/themen/risknews/fehlanzeige-risikomanagement-in-kommunen/85f11f364fb448913174ccc7296eabf7/>
- Sobel, P. J., & Reding, K. F. (2004). Aligning Corporate Governance with Enterprise Risk Management. *Management Accounting Quarterly*, 5(2), 29–37.
- Teel, C., & Verran, J. A. (1991). Factor comparison across studies. *Research in nursing & health*, 14(1), 67–72.
- Thieme, A. (2014). Stadt-Angestellte veruntreut über 430.000 Euro. Retrieved from <http://www.merkur.de/lokales/muenchen/stadt-muenchen/staedtische-angestellte-veruntreut-ueber-430000-euro-mm-3895614.html>
- Weischer, C. (2007). *Sozialforschung*. Konstanz: UVK Verlagsgesellschaft.
- Wengert, H. (2013). *Corporate Risk Management*. Berlin: Springer Gabler.
- Wold, H. (1982). Soft modeling: The basic design and some extensions. In K. G. Jöreskog & H. Wold (Eds.), *Systems Under Indirect Observations: Part I* (pp. 1–54). Amsterdam: North-Holland.
- Woods, M. (2009). A contingency theory perspective on the risk management control system within Birmingham City Council. *Management accounting research*, 20(1), 69–81.
- Yazid, A., Hussin, M., & Daud, W. (2011). An Examination of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) Practices among the Government-Linked Companies (GLCs) in Malaysia. *International Business Research*, 4(4), 94–103. doi:10.1016/j.jaccpubpol.2005.10.001,
- Zhao, X., Hwang, B.-G., & Low, S. (2015). Enterprise risk management in international construction firms: drivers and hindrances. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 22(3), 347–366.